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Transparency Practice and Work Engagement: School Context

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ABSTRACT

Corporate transparency is the achievement of a workplace openly sharing information as a means of leveraging the company and its workers. The study found a correlation between corporate transparency practices of school management or administration and the work engagement of employees. The related literature and studies were reviewed to support the study. The population consists of all the employees of the colleges whereby total enumeration was used. Descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design were applied in the study. The data were gathered through questionnaires and a weighted mean was used to measure the level of corporate transparency practices and work engagement. Pearson r was used to determine the correlation between the two variables. The study found no correlation between corporate transparency practices and work engagement, therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

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Introduction

Following the history of the existence of corporate transparency, this emanated due to corruption. There is no other way to curb corruption except through the implementation of corporate governance via transparency. Its law dictates management's disclosure of practices, activities, policies, and decisions that affect the stockholders or stakeholders.

Transparency has become one of the components of corporate governance which is practiced, not only in the government's office but even in private organizations. There are familiar issues of corruption in the private sectors such as those from Enron, Volkswagen, Lehman Brothers, BP Uber, Apple, Facebook, Valeant Pharmaceuticals, Kobe Steel, and Equifax (Smith, 2018, Sullivan (2001).

Studies found that implementing corporate transparency leads to corporate profitability and an increase in employees' work engagement (Chi (2009), Yu-Chih & Yan (2007), Erick (2007), Arceiz, et.al (2017), Wanjau, et.al (2018), Njeri (2013), Edogbanya & Kamardin (2016), Kim & Yang (2013), Jiang & Luo (2018) and Jiang & Men (2015).

Reading the related studies, the author found nothing conducted related to the implementation of corporate transparency in the school setting and how it affects school performance and employees' work engagement. Hence, this study zeroed in on the school setting practice of transparency and how a transparent management style would affect the work engagement of the employees.

The study is divided into five parts. The first part is the introduction that discusses the rationale or the background of the study and its objective. The second part is the review of related literature which includes related studies on the concept of transparency, transparency in the Philippines government, transparency in the private sector, and how transparency affects corporate performance. The third part is about the methodology of the study which discusses the research design, population of the study, the locale of the study, data gathering instruments, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is empirical data and analysis. This part presents the data that was gathered through questionnaires that were statistically computed and analyzed. The final part is the result, discussion, and conclusion.

Literature Review

The purpose of the literature review is to gain more understanding of the theories of corporate transparency. Thus, this part discusses the theories of the study based on the literature of previous studies.

Transparency's Historical Development

The word transparency draws mixed reactions from both groups: the general public and the government. For employees or the public in general, transparency management lets the public know what is going on and the public can put their trust in the leaders, however, its downside can create a big problem for the management who are not used to revealing their secret dealings or confidential decisions. Ordinary definitions of transparency can be found in the dictionaries such as the Cambridge Dictionary which refers to "the quality of being easy to see through" or Merriam-Webster defines it as "the quality or state of being transparent". Being transparent means "fine or sheer enough to be seen through". These definitions are enough to give a general view. However, the word "transparency" brings different meanings when it is applied to government agencies, NGOs, non-profit organizations, and educational institutions.

The concern for transparency was already traced back to the Watergate incident in 1970 (Ball, 2009). The incident opened the mind of people about the importance of the public, greater access to governmental information and their transaction, and making their decision more open to the public (Vaugh, 2000). As a result of such concern were the laws allowing information to be available to the public such as the Freedom of Information Act (FOIA), (1974), the Presidential Records Act (178), the Whistleblower Protection Act (1989), and the Foreign Corrupt Practices Act (1977). But the word transparency in both public and academic discussions and academic discussion came after supranational organizations, namely European Unions (Ball, 2009, as cited from Lodge, 1994), the General Agreement on Tariff and Trade (Ball, 2009 as cited from Qureshi, 1990), and nongovernmental organizations such as Transparency International (Ball, 2009).

The use of the word transparency became prominent in the 1990s when the manager of the World Bank Peter Eigen felt frustrated with the corruption of countries where it gave loans for their country's development. The concern about corruption led to a wider discussion on how to solve corruption. Subsequently, Peter Eigen realized that he could not solve the problem from within the World Bank and so they need to create a non-governmental organization that will monitor the corruption named Transparency International with Eigen as its head (Eigen, 2003, Holzner & Holzner, 2006, pp. 188-189). The word transparency was spread to the World Bank's policies (Woods, 2001), to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) convention, and to the International Monetary Fund (Toby McIntosh as cited from Roberts, 2006, p. 187). The documents of the IMF became the model for other countries that avail loans from the IMF to adopt. The interconnectedness of the supranational organizations and NGOs popularized the word transparency (Eigen, 2003, pp. 35-42). Its meaning evolved, such as information provided to the public through open decision-making and meetings; honesty, y, and accountability (Ball, 2009 as cited from Stone, 2002, pp. 305-306).

Ball (2009) identifies three metaphors for transparency as a public value, as normal behavior, or as a way to counter corruption. As a public value, people demand information from the government, and non-profit organizations, that their activities should become more open to public scrutiny. The first metaphor emphasizes open decision-making (Ball, 2009). The second metaphor is open government and organization (Ball, 2009, as cited in Piotrowski, 2007). This is about the ease of access and use of government and non-profit information. The third metaphor is related to policy that should be open to the public related to who decides, what decisions are made, and how to use the information (Ball, 2009).

Notably, the trending use of the word, "transparency" speaks about the proper conduct of business in both the private and public sectors (Ball, 2009). The office of the government, the non-profit organization, and the private educational institution have the contextual meaning of transparency.

Transparency in the Philippine Government

According to data reported by UNESCO, countries that have enacted freedom of information laws are on the rise. The data further presented in 2011 that there were only 90 countries that had enacted laws on transparency compared to 2016 which rose to 112 countries (Loesche, 2017). These laws are important to keep their government accountable to the public or the citizens

Since the study is in the Philippine context, there is a need to understand transparency in such a setting. The Philippine government is mandated by the 1987 Constitution particularly section 28, Article II which stipulates the public disclosure of information concerning public interest. In implementing this section, the government has issued Executive Order No. 2, S. 2016, by the office of the President to adopt and implement a policy of full public disclosure of all its transactions involving public interest (President of the Philippines, 2016). Through this Executive Order, the President orders that information related to:

any records, documents, papers, reports, letters, contracts, minutes, and transcripts of official meetings, maps, books, photographs, data, research materials, films, sound and video recording, magnetic or other tapes, electronic data, computer-stored data, any other like or similar data or materials recorded, stored or archived in whatever format, whether offline or online, which are made, received or kept in or under the control and custody of any government office according to law, executive order, and rules and regulations or in connection with the performance or transaction of official business by any government office (Executive Order No. 2, S. 2016, section 1).

The right to information can be denied when the information falls under any of the exceptions enshrined in the Constitution, existing law, or jurisprudence (Executive Order, No. 2, Section 4). Through the executive order, the government is trying to make transparency a public value as pointed out by Ball, (2009) by which government officials are made to be aware that all activities and transactions should be transparent as this serves as the guiding principle of their behaviors in managing their offices. As a matter of their constitutional right, people demand information from the government that their transactions and activities must be open to public scrutiny and this is in line with the original concept of transparency as pointed out by Ball, (2009) as cited from Stone, (2002, pp. 305-306).

Supporting the government's implementation of its transparency efforts, Transparency, and Accountability Networks, an NGO in the Philippines, formed "Bantay Lansangan" or "Road Watch" as an arm of Transparency and Accountability Networks to monitor corruption, particularly in the department of public works and highways. The Bantay Lansangan sends its army to different places to scrutinize the transactions of the Department of Public Works and Highways (Lazatine, 2013).

Transparency in Business Practices

Both government and private sectors commonly refer to transparency as openness, however, its application may vary depending on the nature of the business. Take an example from Distributed Systems which have eight categories of transparency: access, location, concurrency, replication, failure, migration, performance, and scaling (Mantena, n.d, Anthony, 2016, pp. 107-201). In the manufacturing company, transparency can mean that people can see through its internal workings. It provides full access to information required for collaboration and collective management decision-making (Leiva, 2019). This means access to production information, processes, and resources (Biddle, 2005). In terms of school management, transparency means keeping the staff, students, parents, and the community informed about policies and changes that affect them (Leedy, 2018). Transparency makes school administrators accountable to employees, students, parents, and the community.

Asia Society Philippines (2012) emphasized that corruption and cronyism are still widespread in both the private and public sectors of the Philippines. In terms of government corruption, the Philippines recently (2019) ranked 113 of 180 countries which has increased from 99th last 2018 (Trading Economics, 2019). To the private sector, The Global Fraud Survey as cited by Philstar Global (2018), ranked the Philippines 17th among 53 economies with the highest perceived bribery and corruption practices.

In addition, Transparency International (2009) identified the existence of corruption in private businesses or corporations ranging from small entrepreneurs in Sub-Saharan Africa to multinationals from Europe and North America. Forms of corruption include issues such as bribery, corporate fraud, cartels, corruption in supply chains, and transnational transactions. There are numerous examples of corruption scandals found all over the internet such as Enron, Volkswagen, Lehman Brothers, BP Uber, Apple, Facebook, Valeant Pharmaceuticals, Kobe Steel, and Equifax (Smith, 2018). Interestingly, Sullivan (2001) discussed issues of lack of corporate governance such as the BCCI (Bank of Credit and Commercial International) scandal, The United States' saving and loan crisis, the gap between executive compensation and corporate performance, and the Asian financial crisis.

Corporate Transparency Practices in the School Context

Four core principles of corporate governance can be implemented in the school operation, namely fairness, accountability, integrity, and transparency (HKE, 2006). Fairness means all shareholders and stakeholders receive equal treatment from the management or the company (Price, 2018). Accountability refers to the management's responsibility for all activities and presenting a fair, balanced, and understandable assessment of the organization's position and prospects to stakeholders (Andrews, 2017). While integrity can mean doing the right thing or the ability to act honestly and be consistent in whatever one is doing. It can also mean impartiality, avoidance of conflict of interest, confidentiality, and professionalism (CMA, 2017). Lastly, transparency is openness, honesty, and straightforwardness about various companies' operations (Kappel, 2019). The management should be willing to open its book, records of transactions, and other activities to the stakeholder (Fung, 2014). Through it, stakeholders can have confidence in the decision-making process of the company (Price, 2018,).

World Education Forum (2000) as cited in UNESCO (2000) has expressed concern that corruption is a major drain on the effective use of resources for education and should be drastically curbed. Therefore, any attempt to improve the quality of education cannot be successful without solving its corruption problems. Through transparency, the school prevents doing activities that are harmful to students, parents, and employees. It will not be an overstatement if Rashidah (2017, para. 1) claims that "school is an institution where transparency and accountability go hand in hand and should be held as a statutory obligation"; or Cassano's (2017) statement that transparency is one of the components of improving the quality of education. In this case, school administrators should be transparent and accountable to students, parents, and employees or faculty. Briones (2018) as cited in IIEP-UNESCO (2018) explained in her speech at the IIEP-UNESCO conference, that the Philippines is a very strong advocate of freedom of information and in promoting transparency and accountability. In that forum, Briones (2018) further mentioned that corruption is a total barrier to the quality of education.

In line with the objective of the study, the concern of transparency in school management was related to the management process and regulatory process or policymaking system. The management process refers to how the school is managed in terms of its direction and targets and if these are known to employees or faculty. While the regulatory process pertains to how policies are made, and if all employees are aware of these policies.

The Influence of Transparency on the Employees' Work Engagement

School performance or company performance cannot be achieved without employees' engagement in their work. Kahn (1990) as cited in Bakker, et.al.(2010) and (Schaufeli, et.al. 2002, p. 74) pointed out that work engagement is a multidimensional construct that involves the whole self along with three components namely physical, emotional, and cognitive. It means that work engagement is not just about physical engagement but it involves the whole self. It is not just job- burnout ((Maslach & Leiter, 1997); it is also not just a state of mind that may be characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption).

Quinlivan (2014) contended that the bottom line of employee engagement is transparent management. Moreover, Quinlivan (2014) explained that employees who are happy and love their work are more creative, innovative, and dedicated. Proven by his experience, Bamboo (2019) added that workplace transparency supports the long-term success of the company. Through transparency, the management can boost the morale of its employees and build a trusting relationship with the management among employees. Transparency fosters employees' engagement and performance (Bernstein, 2017).

Studies have shown that disengaged employees are not motivated (Musgrove, Ellinger, & Ellinger, 2014), correspondingly, transparency is one of the key factors for employee engagement (Johnston, 2017) hence, management needs to embrace transparency as part of company culture.

The Effect of Transparency on Performance

The importance of transparency cannot be denied in managing a business, otherwise, trust and performance can be affected. Maintaining a transparent management style can boost trust in the workforce leading to productivity or profitability. This is evidenced by the study of Kim, Lee, and Yang (2013) that corporate transparency is positively associated with firm profitability. Similarly, the studies of Chi (2009), Yu-Chih and Yan (2007), Erick (2007), Arceiz, et.al (2017), Wanjau, et.al (2018), Njeri (2013), Edogbanya Kamardin (2016) and Kim and Yang (2013) found that transparency played a vital role in the financial performance of the companies in Taiwan, the UK, Brazil, East Africa, Kenya, Nigeria, and South Korea. These studies discovered that firms with a greater level of transparent governance have a higher firm value and a lower return on assets. Operational transparency is negatively related to firm value while social transparency is positively associated with firm value and profit. Their studies recommended that corporate disclosure practices should be maintained and improved.

Corporate transparency does not only lead to profitability or corporate performance but most importantly it leads to employee engagement. This is evidenced in the study of Jiang and Luo (2018) and Jiang and Men (2015) who found that transparent management and communication with the employees increase trust and employee engagement. All studies related to corporate transparency and the corporate performance had similar findings that the latter equates to an engaged workforce.

Conceptual framework

Source: Source: Salkind (2010)

Figure 1: The conceptual framework depicts the independent and dependent variables which means that any positive changes in the independent variable can have any effect on the dependent variable. Thus, the framework shows a correlation between the independent variables, such as involvement in decision-making, information sharing, and work engagement.

Statement of the Problems

The study established the correlation between corporate transparency and the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. It specifically answered the following questions:

- 1. What are the corporate transparency practices of school management in terms of :**
 - 1.1 employee involvement in decision-making, and*
 - 1.2 information sharing?*
- 2. What is the work engagement of employees in terms of:**
 - 2.1 cognitive work engagement;*
 - 2.2 effective work engagement, and*
 - 2.3 physical work engagement?*
- 3. Is there a relationship between corporate transparency such as involvement in decision-making and information sharing and the three components of work engagement?**

Assumption

The study assumed that corporate transparency motivates employees to engage in their work.

Hypothesis

Studies have found that corporate transparency is not only leading toward financial performance but most likely leads to employees' work engagement (Jiang & Luo (2018), Jiang & Men, 2015) The current study hypothesizes that there is a relationship between corporate transparency and employees' work engagement.

The Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study is limited to measuring the corporate transparency practices of school administrators of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region and employees' work engagement. The variables to be measured are limited to employees' involvement in decision-making and information sharing.

Research Methodology

The study was conducted to investigate the correlation between corporate transparency and the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. This part then, discusses the research design, the locale of the study, the population of the study, data gathering instruments, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The study used a descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design. It is used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, characteristics of people, situations, phenomena, or relationship variables (Ariola, 2006, cited by Abun, 2019). Along this line, the study determined the level of corporate transparency of the administrators and their correlation with the work engagement of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region.

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was the Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos region which is composed of the Divine Word College of Vigan and Divine Word College of Laoag. Divine Word College of Vigan belongs to the Province of Ilocos Sur and is located within the heritage city of Vigan. Divine Word College of Vigan is run by the congregation of the Divine Word Missionaries or known as the Society of the Divine Word or in Latin, *Societas Verbi Divini* (SVD). While Divine Word College of Laoag belongs to Ilocos Norte province and is located in Laoag City.

Population

The population of the study was composed of all employees of Divine Word College of Vigan and Divine Word College of Laoag. Since the total numbers of employees were limited, total enumeration was used as the sampling method.

Data Gathering Instruments

The study utilized questionnaires. The questionnaires were adapted from the Corporate Transparency Checklist of Holtz and Havens (2019) and Clark (2014). The questionnaires were then adjusted to the school context.

Data Gathering Procedures

In the process of data gathering, the researcher sent a letter to the president of the College, requesting him to allow the researcher to conduct the survey. The researcher personally met the president to request employees to answer the questionnaires.

The retrieval of questionnaires was arranged between the president’s representative and the researcher with the help of employees.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean ascertained the level of perception of employees toward corporate transparency practices and Pearson r measured the correlation between transparency practices and work engagement. The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation were used:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation	Overall Descriptive Rating
4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree on	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

Empirical Data and Analysis

The data are presented according to the statement of the problem of the study.

1. What are the corporate transparency practices of school management in terms of :

- 1.1 employee involvement in decision-making, and
- 1.2 information sharing?

Table 1a. Management Transparency as to involvement in Decision Making

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. The top school administrators (President and Vice Presidents) call for regular meetings to discuss issues of the school.	3.33	SWA
2. The top administrators solicit ideas from lower-level administrators and employees to decide on certain issues	3.04	SWA
3. The top administrators involve the employees in setting the vision and mission of the school.	3.14	SWA
4. The top administrators allow the employees to give feedback	3.11	SWA
5. The top administrators never decide alone without the participation of other school administrators or employees.	3.02	SWA
6. The top administrators allow the employees to suggest to the administrators how to solve certain issues	3.02	SWA
7. Top administrators empower lower administrators and employees to make decisions	2.92	SWA
8. The top administrators allow the employees to comment on the decisions through letters or in general assemblies or through the official social media of the school	2.99	SWA
9. Top administrators allow the employees to submit their thoughts and ideas for their regular council meeting.	3.03	SWA
Composite Mean	3.07	SWA

Source: Holtz and Havens (2019) and Clark (2014).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>Somewhat Agree</i>	<i>Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low/High</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	<i>Very Low/Very High</i>

Corporate transparency practices of school management in terms of employee involvement in decision-making gained a 3.07 composite mean which is described as somewhat agree (SWA). In other words, the employees have not been very highly or highly involved in decision-making. Employee involvement in decision-making is only at a moderate level (3.07). Taking the item separately, it demonstrates that all questions under employee involvement in decision-making gained the same evaluation, that employees' involvement is only to a moderate extent. Specifically, the effort of top school administrators (President and Vice Presidents) to call for regular meetings and discuss issues of the school with the employees (3.33), solicit ideas from lower-level administrators and employees to decide on certain issues (3.04), set the vision and mission of the school (3.14), allow the employees to give feedback (3.11), participate in decision making (3.02), allow the employees to suggest to the administrators on how to solve certain issues (3.02), empower lower administrators and employees to make decisions (2.92), allow the employees to comment on the decisions through letters or in general assembly or through official social media of the school (2.99), and to allow the employees to submit their thoughts and ideas for their regular council meeting (3.03)

Table 1b. Management Transparency as to Information Sharing

INDICATORS		Mean	DR
1.	The top administrators inform the employees about the direction of the school	3.12	SWA
2.	The administrators inform the employees and other administrators about the new development plan of the school.	3.06	SWA
3.	The top administrators explain to the employees the rationale of their decisions.	2.95	SWA
4.	The top administrators present issues that affect the employees in the general assembly	2.99	SWA
5.	The administrators allow individual employees to request information related to how they are paid	3.11	SWA
6.	Top administrators inform the employees of the decisions they have made	3.10	SWA
7.	Top administrators disseminate information coming from Commission on Higher Education to employees	3.24	SWA
8.	Top administrators post regular news update that affects the school and employees	3.17	SWA
9.	Top administrators allow open communication with the employees without any barriers	3.02	SWA
Composite Mean		3.08	SWA

Source: Holtz and Havens (2019) and Clark (2014).

It is the same case for the evaluation of information sharing. As gleaned from the table, it reveals that as a whole, corporate transparency practices of school management in terms of information sharing garnered a composite mean of 3.08 which is interpreted as somewhat agree (SWA) or moderate extent. It indicates that the management or administrators have not been very highly sharing information with the employees. Even when the questions under information sharing are taken singly, they have the same level of evaluation. Particularly, the effort of management or administrators to inform the employees about the direction of the school (3.12), inform the employees and other administrators about the new development plan of the school (3.06), explain to the employees the rationale of their decisions (2.95), present issues that affect the employees in the general assembly (2.99), allow individual employees to request for information related to how they are paid (3.11), inform the employees of the decisions they have made

(3.10), disseminate information coming from Commission on Higher Education to employees (3.24), post regular news update that affects the school and employees (3.17) and to allow open communication with the employees without any barriers (3.02) are all evaluated as somewhat agree (SWA) or moderate extent.

Table 1c. Summary of the Transparent Management Style

ITEMS	Mean	DR
1. Employee Involvement in Decision Making	3.07	SWA
2. Information Sharing	3.08	SWA
Overall Mean	3.08	SWA

In summary, the table shows that corporate transparency practices of school management or administrators are within the range of 3.08 which is interpreted as somewhat agree (SWA) or moderate extent. It concludes that the management or school administrators have not been very highly or highly practicing corporate transparency in terms of employees' involvement in decision-making (3.07) and information sharing (3.08).

2. What is the work engagement of employees in terms of:

- 2.1 cognitive work engagement;
- 2.2 effective work engagement, and
- 2.3 physical work engagement?

Table 2a. Employees' Work Engagement as to Cognitive Work Engagement

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. My mind is often full of ideas about my work.	3.81	A
2. My mind is fully engaged with my work.	3.83	A
3. I have an idea about how to perform my work better.	3.91	A
4. I search for new ways to improve my knowledge related to my work.	3.90	A
5. My thoughts are fully focused when thinking about my work.	3.76	A
Composite Mean	3.84	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017), Abun, et.al. (2020)

The evaluation of work engagement is higher than the evaluation of corporate transparency practices of school management or administrators. As reflected on the table, it reveals that the employees' work engagement along with cognitive work engagement is 3.84 which is interpreted as agree (A) or high. It means that as a whole, employees' knowledge about their work is considered high. The employees know their job. Even when the items under this dimension are taken separately, they are all rated highly. Particularly, employees have full ideas about their work (3.81), have an idea about how to perform their work better(3.91), are fully engaged with their work (3.83), fully focused when thinking about their work (3.76) and search for new ways to improve their knowledge related to their work (3.90).

Table 2b. Employees' Work Engagement as to Emotional Work Engagement

Indicators	Mean	DR
1. I feel very delighted about what I am doing whenever I am working.	3.73	A
2. I am excited to do my work.	3.76	A
3. I feel good about the work that I do.	3.82	A
4. I am always very enthusiastic to perform my work.	3.86	A
5. I feel very happy when I carry out my responsibilities at work.	3.84	A
Composite Mean	3.80	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017), Abun, et.al. (2020)

The result of the evaluation of the second dimension of work engagement is within the same range as the first dimension. As it is indicated in the table, it appears that as a whole, employees' work engagement in terms of emotional work engagement gained the composite mean of 3.80 which indicates that employees agree (A) to all the questions

presented in the table. It means that as a whole employees agree that they are emotionally engaged in their work. This evaluation is reflected throughout the questions, especially employees feel delighted about what they are doing whenever they are working (3.73), are excited to do their work (3.76), enthusiastic to perform their work (3.86), and happy when they carry out their responsibilities at work (3.84).

Table 2c. Employees' Work Engagement as to Physical Work Engagement

Indicators	Mean	DR
1. No matter how much I work, I still have a high level of energy.	3.43	A
2. I have a great deal of stamina for my work.	3.60	A
3. I have a lot of energy for my work.	3.71	A
4. I am frequently energized by my work.	3.67	A
5. Though my work is physically challenging, I am still excited to do it.	3.70	A
Composite Mean	3.62	A

Source: Kuok and Taormina (2017), Abun, et.al. (2020)

The last dimension of work engagement is the physical aspect. Based on the data, it manifests that employees' physical engagement gained a composite mean of 3.62 which means that employees agree (A) to all questions in this dimension. It means that the employees are physically engaged in their work. Taking the questions separately, they are rated within the same evaluation interpreted as "agree" (A). Particularly, even how much they work, they still have a high level of energy (3.43), have a great deal of stamina for their work (3.60), a lot of energy for their work (3.71), are frequently energized by their work and are still excited to do their work even though the work is physically challenging (3.70).

Table 2d. Summary of Work Engagement

ITEMS	Mean	DR
Cognitive Work Engagement (CWE)	3.84	A
Emotional Work Engagement (EWE)	3.80	A
Physical Work Engagement (PWE)	3.62	A
Overall Mean	3.75	A

In summary, the work engagement of employees obtained an overall mean rating of 3.75 which is considered high. It means that employees are highly engaged cognitively, emotionally, and physically.

3. Is there a relationship between corporate transparency such as involvement in decision-making and information sharing and the three components of work engagement?

Table 3. Relationship between Management Style and Work Engagement

		Cognitive WE	Emotional WE	Physical WE	Work Engagement As a Whole
Involvement	Pearson Correlation	.002	.097	.097	.074
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.973	.185	.185	.313
	N	187	187	187	187
Information Sharing	Pearson Correlation	.032	.136	.106	.103
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.660	.063	.147	.162
	N	187	187	187	187

Management Style As a Whole	Pearson Correlation	.018	.122	.106	.092
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.810	.097	.148	.210
	N	187	187	187	187

In terms of the correlation between corporate transparency practices of school management or administrators and work engagement, the data reveals no correlation between the two variables. It means that the employees’ work engagement does not affect corporate transparency practices. In this case, the work engagement of employees might be affected by other factors outside of the context of the study.

Results and Discussion

The purpose of the study was to find out the correlation between the corporate transparency of school management or administrators and the work engagement of employees. The results indicate that there is no correlation between the two variables. It means that even though there are improvements in corporate transparency practices of school management, it does not make any changes to the work engagement of employees. Based on the result of the study, employees are engaged in their work despite not being highly or very highly involved in decision-making and having limited information about their school.

The high work engagement of employees can be caused by other factors such as performance evaluation bonuses, personal motivation of employees, or other working environment factors. It is noteworthy that corporate transparency is the achievement of a workplace openly sharing information as a means of leveraging the company and its workers. The management then needs to create a healthier and more cohesive workplace by taking the first step of enhancing transparency practices as this helps employees thrive and perform at their best.

Conclusion

The study hypothesized that there is a relationship between corporate transparency practices of school management and the work engagement of employees, but the results showed no correlation between the two variables. Therefore the hypothesis was rejected.

The study had limited variables identified in the corporate transparency practices. Future studies may need to include more dimensions of corporate transparency practices.

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